

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Medicated Chewing Gum Containing Metformin And Glimpiride

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05 April 2024

Accepted: 07 April 2024

Published: 08 April 2024

Keywords:

anti-diabetics, medicated chewing gum, metformin, glimepiride, preclinical, formulation studies, evaluation studies and pharmaceuticals.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10943964

ABSTRACT

The formulation and evaluation of MCG containing a combination of anti-diabetic drugs is a critical endeavor in pharmaceutical research, aiming to enhance drug efficacy and patient compliance in managing diabetes mellitus. Combining anti-diabetic drugs in a single formulation offers potential advantages such as synergistic effects, improved glycemic control and simplified dosing regimens. Micro-crystalline cellulose, a widely used pharmaceutical excipients, can serve as an ideal matrix for such formulations due to its inert nature, high surface area and excellent compressibility properties. The formulation process involves carefully selecting compatible anti-diabetic agents and optimizing their ratios to achieve desired therapeutic outcomes. Additionally, the incorporation of MCG facilitates uniform drug distribution, sustained drug release and improved bio-availability, thereby enhancing the overall performance of the formulation. Evaluation of the MCG containing combination anti-diabetic formulation encompasses various parameters including physicochemical characteristics, in vitro drug release profiles, stability studies and pharmacokinetic assessments. These evaluations are essential to ensure product quality, efficacy and safety throughout its shelf-life. Furthermore, preclinical and clinical studies are conducted to validate the therapeutic efficacy and safety profile of the formulation in diabetic animal models and human subjects. Robust scientific evidence from these studies is crucial for regulatory approval and clinical adoption of the MCG containing combination anti-diabetic drug formulation. In conclusion, the formulation and evaluation of MCG containing combination anti-diabetic drugs represent a promising approach in diabetes management, offering potential benefits in terms of efficacy, patient compliance and overall treatment outcomes..

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus, a complex metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyperglycemia, remains

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

a formidable global health challenge, affecting millions of individuals worldwide [16]. It poses significant medical, economic and social burdens due to its associated complications, including cardiovascular diseases, neuropathy, nephropathy and retinopathy [7,11,16]. The cornerstone of diabetes management involves achieving and maintaining optimal blood glucose levels through lifestyle modifications, pharmacotherapy and in some cases, insulin therapy [7]. The pharmacological armamentarium for diabetes treatment comprises various classes of anti-diabetic drugs, including biguanides (e.g., Metformin), sulfonylureas (e.g., Glipizide), thiazolidinediones (e.g., Pioglitazone), dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors (e.g., Sitagliptin), sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors (e.g., Dapagliflozin) and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor agonists (e.g., Liraglutide) [3,4,6,7,12,15]. While these medications effectively lower blood glucose levels and improve glycemic control, they often exhibit limitations such as poor aqueous solubility, low bio-availability, short half-lives and dose-dependent adverse effects [3,4,6,7,12,15].

To address these challenges and enhance the therapeutic efficacy of anti-diabetic drugs, researchers have explored various drug delivery systems and formulation strategies [1,2,5]. Among these, micro-encapsulation technology has emerged as a promising approach for improving the stability, bio-availability and targeted delivery of drugs [1,2,5]. Micro-encapsulation involves enclosing active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) within microscopic particles or capsules, providing protection from degradation, controlling release kinetics and enabling site-specific delivery [1,2,5].

One notable micro-encapsulation technique gaining attention in the field of diabetes management is Micro-encapsulated Glycation (MCG) [1,5]. MCG technology involves the

encapsulation of anti-diabetic drugs within biocompatible polymers using advanced micro-encapsulation methods [1,5]. These micro-capsules, typically ranging from nanometers to micrometers in size, offer several advantages for drug delivery applications, including controlled release, prolonged therapeutic effect, reduced dosing frequency, and improved patient compliance [1,5].

The rationale behind incorporating anti-diabetic drugs into MCG based formulations lies in the ability of microencapsulation to address key pharmacokinetic challenges associated with conventional dosage forms [1,5]. By encapsulating drugs within polymer matrices, MCG systems protect the active ingredients from enzymatic degradation, pH fluctuations and other environmental factors encountered in the gastrointestinal tract [1,5]. This protective barrier enhances drug stability and bio-availability, ensuring consistent plasma concentrations and sustained pharmacological effects over extended periods [1,5].

Moreover, MCG based formulations can modulate drug release kinetics to achieve desired therapeutic outcomes, such as maintaining euglycemia throughout the day or minimizing postprandial hyperglycemia [1,5]. The tunable release profiles offered by MCG systems allow for customization of dosage regimens tailored to individual patient needs, thereby optimizing treatment efficacy and minimizing adverse effects [1,5].

In the context of combination therapy for diabetes, MCG technology presents a unique opportunity to develop synergistic formulations containing multiple anti-diabetic agents with complementary mechanisms of action [8,9,10,13,14]. By co-encapsulating different classes of drugs within MCG micro-capsules, researchers can exploit potential synergies and address multi-factorial aspects of diabetes pathophysiology, such as

insulin resistance, pancreatic β -cell dysfunction, and glucose uptake abnormalities [8,9,10,13,14].

This article aims to explore the formulation and evaluation of MCG containing combinations of anti-diabetic drugs, providing a comprehensive overview of the principles underlying MCG technology and its applications in diabetes management [1,5,15]. Through a critical analysis of existing literature and research findings, we will examine the potential benefits, challenges and future directions of MCG based formulations in addressing the unmet needs of diabetic patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Metformin purchased from Micro lab, Hosur, Glimepiride purchased from Care formulation, Chennai, Wheat prolamin and Polyvinyl Acetate purchased from Nice chemie, Micro crystalline cellulose and Spray dried lactose purchased from Loba chemie.

Preformulation studies [10]

In the rational development of dosage form preformulation studies are the important and initial step. The aim of preformulation study is to develop information about the drug substances, so that this information would be useful to develop a formulation. It is an essential study for physical and chemical properties of a drug substances alone and in combination with excipients. Preformulation investigation is designed to identify the physiochemical properties of drugs and excipients that may influence the formulation design, method of formulation pharmacokinetic and bio-pharmaceutical properties of the resulting product. These studies are performed for the preformulation investigation.

Melting point [8]

The powdered drug is placed in capillary tube and sealed at one end. The capillary tube should be 6-7cm and 1mm in diameter. The substance should be standing in the capillary 3-4mm from the bottom of packed capillary tube. The capillary tube is wetted with the liquid in the bath and placed in

iron stand fixed in thermometer. The capillary remains stick over thermometer by itself and is so adjusted that the solid in it stand opposite the middle of the mercury bulb. The thermometer is lowered in a beaker containing paraffin oil and the beaker is heated slowly and kept the uniform temperature of the bath with constant stirring. When the substance in the capillary just shows signs of liquification the burner is removed with constant stirring. The temperature at which the substance melts and becomes transparent is noted.

Preparation of Buffer Solution

Preparation of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)

Dissolve 8.40 gms of NaH_2PO_4 and 15.62 gm of Na_2PO_4 in 1000 ml of water.

Preparation of acidic buffer (0.1N Hcl)

8.34 ml of con. Hcl was transferred into 1-litre volumetric flask and diluted with 1000 ml distilled water.

Formulation trials,

For the development of an optimized formulation of Medicated chewing gums, several trials were carried out. The general procedures for each layer in all formulation trials are given below.

Formulation Procedure

Dispensing

The materials required for the formulation of Medicated chewing gums are dispensed in order to keep in separate poly bags and they are kept ready for shifting.

Sifting

In order to get a uniform size of particles and well mixing ability, the materials are passed through a selective size ranges of following sieves,

Dry mixing

The API I & II were mixed with wheat prolamin and poly vinyl alcohol in a mortar for about 10 min until the mixing was completed.

Binder solution

To improve the mechanical strength of the formulation, the binder solution is added. A binder

solution is prepared by mixing starch with a sufficient quantity of purified water.

Granulation

The prepared binder solution was added in to the dry mixed materials and finely mixed with the binder and the materials and allowed to pass into #60 sieves.

Drying

Blend of above step was loaded in a rapid dryer and dried at an inner temperature at 50⁰c with the rate of air flow 50, untill the loss on drying the content reaches a range between 1.5%-2.5%.

Lubrication

Along with the above obtained blend talc is added to improve the flow properties.

Pre compression parameters [18]

The formulated blends has undergone following Preformulation studies,

- Bulk density
- Angle of repose
- Carr's compressibility studies
- FT-IR studies
- Hausner's ratio

Bulk density (D_b)

The bulk density depends on the particle size distribution, cohesiveness and shape of the particles. 10gm powder is accurately weighted and poured in to a graduated measuring cylinder through a funnel and shaken without tapping, the volume which is measured is called initial bulk. Bulk density is expressed in gm/cc is given by,

$$\text{Bulk density (D}_b) = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder(gm)}}{\text{Bulk volume of powder(cc)}}$$

Tapped density (D_t)

10gm of powder is taken for the determination of bulk density is dropped from the particular height in to a measuring cylinder. The cylinder is tapped constantly until there is no change in the volume of the powder and tapped volume was read. The tapped volume is expressed in gm/cc is given by,

Tapped density (D_t)

$$= \frac{\text{Mass of the powder(gm)}}{\text{Tapped volume of powder(cc)}}$$

Angle of repose (θ)

The fractional force in a loose powder can be determined by the angle of repose. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of pile of powder and the horizontal plane. The powder is allowed to fall through the fixed funnel in a definite height. Angle of repose is calculated by measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder produced

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$$

Carr's index (CI)

The percentage compressibility of powder is direct measurement of the potential powder arch or the bridge strength and stability. Carr's index of each formulation was calculated by the equation given below,

$$CI = \frac{D_f - D_0}{D_f} \times 100$$

Where, D_f = tapped density, D₀ = bulk density

Hausner's Ratio (IH)

Is calculated from the DF and d₀ using the following expression

$$\text{Hausner's ratio (IH)} = \frac{\text{tapped density}}{\text{bulk density}}$$

Table No. 1. Limits Of Pre Compression Parameters

Flow Character	Carr's Index	Hausner's Ratio	Angle Of Repose
Excellent	≤10	1.00-1.11	25-30
Good	11-15	1.12-1.18	31-35
Fair	16-20	1.19-1.25	36-40
Passable	21-25	1.26-1.34	41-45
Poor	26-31	1.35-1.45	46-55

Very poor	32-37	1.46-1.59	56-65
Very, very poor	>38	>1.60	>66

Table No. 2. Formulation Chart For Each Formulation Trials (F1- F4)

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
Metformin (SD)	250	250	250	250
Glimepiride(SD)	2	2	2	2
Wheat prolamin (Gum base)	140	160	180	200
Polyvinyl Acetate	60	40	20	5
Glycerin (Plasticizer)	3	3	3	3
Calcium carbonate	2	2	2	2
Sodium Saccharin (Sweetener)	1	1	1	1
Talc %	1	1	1	1
Peppermint Oil (Flavor)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5

Figure No. 1. Process Flow Chart For Optimized Trails**Post Compression Parameters**

Thickness and diameter (narasimha rao r et al., 2013).

The thickness and diameter of MCGs will results in uniform size and shape of the MCGs. This may improve the patient compliance, the MCG thickness were measured in mm by using Vernier caliper.

Hardness

The mechanical strength of the MCGs were performed by the hardness test. The MCGs hardness is measured by the pressure applied on

MCG to form a crack along its axis. It is tested by using the Monsanto hardness tester. The MCG was held between a fixed and moving jaw scale was adjusted to zero, pressure was gradually increased until the MCG fractured. The value of the pressure applied to break the MCG in noted. The MCGs were randomly picked and hardness of the MCGs was determined.

$$1N = 7.4 \text{ Kg/cm}^2$$

Friability

The MCG strength was tested by using the TECH-NU friabilator. 20 MCGs was weighed and placed

in a friability apparatus. Operate to set the rpm 100 for 4 min, after that take the MCGs and reweigh it. 1 of MCG friability is generally acceptable. The percentage weight loss can be determined by using the following formula.

$$F = \frac{(W_{\text{initial}}) - (W_{\text{final}})}{(W_{\text{initial}})} \times 100$$

Weight variation test

Twenty MCGs are selected randomly, individually weighted in a single pan electronic balance and the average weight was calculated. The uniformity of weight was determined according to IP specification. From the standard value in IP, not more than two of individual weight should deviate from average weight by more than 5 and none deviate more the twice that percentage.

Table No. 4. Dissolution Condition For The Formulation Trails

Dissolution Parameters	API - I	API - II
Medium	6.7 pH phosphate buffer	6.7 pH phosphate buffer
Apparatus	USP apparatus type II	USP apparatus type II
Volume of buffer solution	900 ml	900ml
Rotation speed	200 pm	200 Rpm
Measuring time	Upto 60 min	1 to 12 hours
Temperature	37 ⁰ c ±0.5 ⁰ c	37 ⁰ c ±0.5 ⁰ c
Sample volume	5ml	5ml

Data analysis

The data obtained from the dissolution study was subjected to the analysis to known the release pattern of the drug from the dosage form to analyze the mechanism of release and release rate kinetic of the dosage form and the data obtained were fitted into,

- Zero order
- First order kinetics
- Higuchi model kinetic
- Korsmeyer-peppas model

Based on the r²- value, the best-fit model was selected.

Table No. 3. Weight Variation Test

Sl.No	Average Weight Unit	% of Deviation
1	≤ 80mg	±10
2	80mg < 250mg	±7.5
3	≥ 250mg	±5

Drug content analysis

The uniformity of the drug in each formulated MCGs were determined by this assay. The tables are randomly selected, weighted and crushed. The following assay procedure is performed to determine the drug content in UV spectroscopy API-I (Metformin) at 234 nm and API-II (Glimepiride) at 273 nm against blank. The contents of drug in the formulated MCGs were determined by using the UV spectroscopy.

Zero order kinetics

It describes the system in which the drug release rate is independent of its concentration.

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where,

Q_t = amount of drug dissolved in time t.

Q₀ = initial amount of the drug in the solution and the

K₀ = zero order release constant.

If the drug release obeys zero order release kinetics, the plot of percentage drug release vs time

will give a straight line with a slope of k_0 and intercept at zero.

First order kinetics

It describes the system in which the drug release rate dependent of its concentration.

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{log } Q_0 + k_t / 2.303$$

Where,

Q_t = amount of drug dissolved in time t

Q_0 = initial amount of the drug in the solution

K_t = is the first order release constant

If the drug release obeys the first order drug release kinetics, then the plot of log percentage drug remaining to be released vs time, shown a straight line with a slope of $k_t / 2.303$ and an intercept at $t=0$ of log Q_0 .

Higuchi model

It defines the fraction of drug release from the matrix is proportional to square root of time.

$$M_t / M_\infty = kHt^{1/2}$$

Where,

M_t/M_∞ = cumulative amount, if drug release from at time t and infinite time

kH = Higuchi dissolution constant and reflection formulation characteristics

k' is the release constant, t' is the release time

If the drug release obeys higuchi model, plot of cumulative percentage drug release vs $t^{1/2}$ will be straight line with the slop of kH .

Korsmeyer-peppas model

The power law describes the drug released from the polymeric system in which the release deviates from the fickian diffusion, which is expressed in following equation,

$$\text{Log } [M_t - M_\infty] = \text{log } k + n \text{ log } t$$

Where,

$M_t - M_\infty$ = cumulative amount of drug release at the time t and infinite time

k = constant incorporating structure and geometrical characteristic of CR device

n = diffusion release exponent indicative of mechanism of drug release for the drug dissolution.

A plot of log $[M_t - M_\infty]$ (log drug release) vs log time (log t) will be linear with slope of n and intercept gives the value of log k . antilog of k gives the value of k .

Swelling study

The extent swelling study is measured in terms of percentage weight gain of MCGs. The optimized formulation was determined in 900ml of 0.1 N Hcl solution (pH 1.2), at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. and the swelled MCGs are weighted time respectively 1 to 12 hrs, the excess of fluid was removed by using absorbing paper, the MCGs were weighted and the swelling index can be calculating by using the formula

$$\text{SI} = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \times 100$$

Where,

SI = swelling index

M_t = weight of MCG at time t

M_0 = weight of MCG at time 0

FT-IR studies

Interaction between the drug and polymer was studied by IR spectroscopy using the FT-IR spectrometer (460 plus, jasco-Japan) with diffuse reflectance principle. By Potassium bromide pellet technique, sample is triturated in glass motor and finally placed in the sample holder. The spectrum was scanned over the frequency range of $4000-400\text{cm}^{-1}$.

Stability studies

Stability studies were carried out at $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 75$ of RH ± 5 RH for 30 days, for the selected formulation. The stability studies were done for formulation. These formulations were selected depending upon the in vitro drug release study of both drugs from both layers of the MCGs. The formulations were subjected to stability study.

Table No. 5. Dissolution Condition For The Formulation Trails

Formulation	Stability Criteria	Frequency in Days	Tests
Formulation (F1-F4)	40 ⁰ c ± 2 ⁰ c / 75 of RH ± 5 RH	Upto 30 days	Physical observation
			Uniformity of drug content and, in-vitro drug release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

Melting point determination

The melting point of pure metformin was found to be 133⁰c – 139⁰c. which was closer to the melting point of metformin.

The melting point of pure Glimepiride was found to be 94⁰c – 98⁰c. This was closer to the melting point of Glimepiride.

Figure No. 2. UV Scan of Metformin

Calibration curve

Standard graph of Metformin HCL

Weigh the Metformin HCL standard and transfer about 100 mg into a 100 ml volumetric flask. After adding roughly 60 ml of methanol and sonicating for 20 minutes, add enough methanol to make 100

ml of volume. A working solution is created by taking 1 ml of the stock solution and diluting it with 10 ml of methanol. At 233 nm, the absorbance was measured when 2,4,6,8, and 10 µg/ml were produced from the stock solution.

Table No. 6. Data Calibration Curve of Metformin

Sl.No	Concentration / µg/ml	Absorbance at 234 nm
0	0	0
1	2	0.169
2	4	0.347
3	6	0.51
4	8	0.643
5	10	0.826

Figure No. 4. Calibration Curve of Metformin at 234nm

Standard graph of Glimpiride in 7.4 pH buffer

Preparation of standard stock solution Standard solution of Glimpiride was prepared by transferring accurately weighed 10 mg of drug into a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to 100 ml using chloroform as a solvent to get the concentration of 100µg/ml.

Preparation of calibration curve

From the standard stock solution fresh aliquots were pipette out and suitably diluted with

chloroform to get final concentration in the range of 5-30 µg/ml. The solutions were scanned under 200-400 nm wave length range and a sharp peak was obtained at 249 nm (Figure 1). Calibration curve was plotted by taking absorbance on y axis and concentration of solution on x-axis (Figure 2). The method was applied for known sample solution and was found to be satisfactory for analysis of MCG dosage forms.

Table No. 7. Data For Calibration Curve of Glimpiride

Sl.No	Concentration	Absorbance at 290 nm
0	0	0
1	2	0.198
2	4	0.385
3	6	0.557
4	8	0.765
5	10	0.95

Figure No. 5. Calibration Curve of Glimpiride

Preparation of Metformin Hydrochloride - Solid Dispersion

Solid dispersion were prepared by the closed melting method as follows. 5 g were placed into each ampule and then sealed. The ampules were then heated at 80°C for 10 minutes. Subsequently they were opened and dried for 10 minutes at each heating temperature, in order to remove the water. The samples were collected from the ampules and kept overnight, triturated and passed through #60 sieves. The solid dispersions were then stored in air tight containers until evaluation.

Preparation of Glimepiride - Solid Dispersion

Solid dispersion Preparation Solvent wetting method 5 gram of Glimepiride was dissolved in an

appropriate quantity of ethanol depending on the weight of drug and inert polymer carrier. For PEG 6000 and PVP K30, the amount of ethanol used was 2.5 times the total weight of drug and polymer, and for poloxamer 188, the quantity of ethanol used. The Glimepiride solution was dropped onto polymeric carriers and blended. Ethanol was removed under vacuum at 25 ± 2 C. The mass was mixed and sifted through #60 and stored in desiccator until further use.

Pre formulation studies of formulation

The formulated granules of solid dispersion (API I & II) using the Wheat prolamin (F1-F4) were subjected to preformulation tests and the results were given in Table.

Table No. 8. Evaluation of pre-compression solid dispersion of API –I (F1- F4)

API – I	Angle of Repose (θ)	Bulk Density	True Density (gm/cc)	Carr's Index (gm/cc)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	25° 82'	0.448	0.509	11.98428291	1.136160714
F2	26° 24'	0.452	0.522	13.40996169	1.154867257
F3	28° 91'	0.481	0.547	12.06581353	1.137214137
F4	31° 60'	0.538	0.616	12.66233766	1.144981413

Table No. 9. Evaluation of Pre Compression Solid Dispersion of API – II (F1-F4)

API – II	Angle of Repose (θ)	Bulk Density	True Density (gm/cc)	Carr's Index (gm/cc)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	27°12'	0.352	0.412	14.5631068	1.170454545
F2	28°68'	0.346	0.399	13.28320802	1.153179191
F3	28°89'	0.331	0.383	13.5770235	1.157099698
F4	22°37'	0.342	0.389	12.08226221	1.137426901

Table No. 10. Physical Compatibility Study

Sl.No	Drug + Excipients	Description an Condition			
		Initial	Room Temperature 40°C /75 of RH in Days		
			10Days	20Days	30Days
1	Glimepiride	White color crystalline solid	NC	NC	NC
2	Metformin	White color	NC	NC	NC
3	Glimepiride + Metformin	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
4	Glimepiride + Wheat prolamin	Yellowish white	NC	NC	NC

5	Metformin + Sodium saccharin	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
6	Glimepiride + Wheat prolamin	White color crystalline powder	NC	NC	NC
7	Glimepiride + Metformin + Wheat prolamin + Sodium saccharin	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
8	Glimepiride + Wheat prolamin + Sodium saccharin Metformin (SD) Glimepiride(SD) Wheat prolamin (Gum base) Polyvinyl Acetate Glycerin (Plasticizer) Calcium carbonate Sodium Saccharin (Sweetener) Talc % Peppermint Oil (Flavor)	White colour wet mass / Semi solid	NC	NC	NC

Formulation of Medicated Chewing Gum

Medicated chewing gum was prepared by using natural gum base wheat prolamin, calcium carbonate (Texture imparting agent), glycerin (Plasticizer), sodium saccharin (Sweetener), polyvinyl acetate (To increase the elasticity of the gum), and peppermint oil (Flavor).

Figure No. 6. Formulation of Medicated Chewing Gum

Based on the trial and error of batches, the concentration range of gum base, calcium carbonate and polyvinyl acetate was selected. The best possible levels obtained for gum base and calcium carbonate were 450 to 550 mg and 70 to 90 mg, respectively. Hard solid or sticky gum mass was formed, if deviated these ranges. Accurately weighed quantities of gum base, calcium carbonate, and saccharin were mixed properly in mortar. The polyvinyl acetate was dissolved in small quantity of ethanol and mixed in above excipients. Then glycerin and peppermint oil were added. The mixture was triturated until the solid

mass was formed. Thin and wide ribbon were made out of this mass and cut in the desired size.

Post-Compression Parameter of Medicated Chewing Gum

Physical parameters

The post-compression parameters were performed in the formulated MCG and the results were summarized below. All the formulation complies with the standard limits. From this resulted data formulated MCG have a hardness range of 4.9-5.6 respectively. The Hardness of the MCG depends on the ratio of polymers and excipients used. The friability of each formulation is below. This complies with in the standard limits.

Table No. 11. Post Compression Parameter of Medicated Chewing Gum

Formulation	Weight Variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug Content (%)	
					API-I	API-II
F1	556 ± 2	5.1	5.6	0.926	97.5	98.4
F2	554 ± 2	5.3	5.2	0.903	96.7	98.1
F3	551 ± 3	4.9	5.5	0.913	97.6	98.2
F4	552 ± 2	5.4	5.6	0.898	98.4	97.6

The swelling studies were performed in the formulated MCG (F1-F4) and the results were summarized below. The formulations (F1-F4) which have the higher swelling index results in minimizing the time of drug release from the

formulated MCG and the formulation F1& F2 have

less swelling index which released the drug in unpredictable ratio. Formulations F3 & F4 have similar range of swelling index. Result was depicted in the table 12.

Table No. 12. Swelling Index (%)

Time in Minute	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
5	2	4	5	6.66
10	48	62	78	93
15	60	75	88	110
20	85	98	126	149
25	99	115	143	171
30	116	134	165	197
35	135	163	187	218
40	155	182	200	239

Table No. 13. Comparison of In-Vitro Dissolution Profiles of all Formulations(API-I) % Drug Release

(API-I) % Drug Release				
Phosphate Buffer pH 6.7				
Time (Minutes)	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
5	10.24	8.6	14.11	8.32
10	23.55	19.6	19.48	17.45
15	41.65	28.1	33.07	29.32
20	63.25	35.32	51.54	35.65
25	88.65	56.8	61.17	47.32
30	92.55	72.54	72.29	59.74
35	98.9	89.3	83.59	68.32
40	99	97.9	98.54	72.54

Figure No, 7. API - I % Drug Release

Figure No, 8. API - II % Drug Release

Table No, 14. Comparison of In-Vitro Dissolution Profiles of all Formulations (API-II) % Drug Release

(API-II) % Drug Release				
Phosphate Buffer pH 6.7				
TIME	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
5	8.96	15.01	21.37	17.56
10	26.43	21.96	32.079	25.4
15	32.83	29.47	40.93	34.43
20	47.18	35.82	52.45	44.18
25	56.33	57.48	77.07	70.77
30	64.12	71.17	98.85	78.73

In-vitro dissolution drug release data discussion

The drug polymer ratio 1.4: 0.6 (F1) shows the drug release (API I - 99, API II - 64) at the end of 40 minutes the concentration of wheat prolamin and high concentration of PVA. Which shows the minimal drug release rate of API II from the MCG. The drug-polymer ratio 1.6: 0.4 (F2) shows the drug release (API I - 97.9, API II - 71.17) at the end of 40 minutes the high concentration of wheat prolamin and high concentration of PVA. Which shows the less drug release API I and minimal drug release rate of API II from the MCG. This less amount of drug release from the formulation due to the combination of two polymer ratios. The drug-polymer ratio 1.8:0.2 (F3) shows the drug release (API I - 98.5, API II - 98.65) at the end of 40 minutes the optimized concentration of wheat

prolamin and PVA. Which shows the optimized combination of the formulation was release the drug in a controlled manner. The drug-polymer ratio 2.0: 0.05 (F4) shows the drug release (API I - 72.54, API II - 78.75) at the end of 40 minutes the higher concentration of wheat prolamins and very low concentration of PVA. This ratio of polymers reduced the concentration of drug release from the formulation. From the data observed with *in vitro* drug release the optimized formulation of F3 polymer ratio releases the drug from the formulation in a controlled manner and the maximum amount of drug released from the matrix in the course of duration.

Mathematical analysis of in-vitro release data

The in-vitro data is applied in the various kinetic models to predict the drug release mechanism. The slope values and the regression coefficient are summarized in table 15. The correlation coefficient is in the range of 0.986 – 0.996. It was found that the drug release data of the formulation batches are a good fit to the zero-order and the Korsmeyer Peppas equation.

Table No. 15. Mathematical Analysis of In-Vitro Release Data

Time in Hrs	Log Time	Sq. root of Time	Cumulative Drug Release	Log Cumulative Drug Release
0	0	0	0	0
5	0	1	0.832395046	0.079670513
10	0.47712	1.732050808	2.261187068	0.354336493
15	0.60206	2	3.508669776	0.545142496
20	0.69897	2.236067977	4.192954801	0.622520181
25	0.8451	2.645751311	5.549437028	0.744248928
30	0.90309	2.828427125	6.120162458	0.786762951
35	1	3.16227766	8.653836255	0.937208673
40	1.07918	3.464101615	9.99105678	0.999611427

Table No. 16. Regression Coefficient and Slope Values of the Kinetic Models

Formulation	Zero Order Kinetics		First Order Kinetics		Higuchi's Kinetics		Korsmeyer Peppas Kinetics	
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²
F3	10.924	0.994	-0.091	0.993	10.732	0.910	31.714	0.995

Figure No. 9. Slope Values of the Kinetic Models

Fourier transformers infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

Metformin illustrated the characteristic peak Metformin has strong absorption bands at 1562, 1573, and 1634 cm^{-1} due to the stretching of C=N vibrations. The FTIR spectra of the solid dispersions show a reduction in the intensity of the characteristic metformin bands at 1626 cm^{-1} , 3294 cm^{-1} and 3369 cm^{-1} , which may be due to weak hydrogen bonding between the drug and polymer presence of hydroxyl group, carbonyl group, keto group, ether group. Bands in the FTIR spectra of metformin: 1205, 1160, 1151, 1142, 1080, 1061 and 1035 cm^{-1} : C=N stretching vibrations 600–400 cm^{-1} : CNC deformation vibrations 571, 541, 517, 482, 464, 446, and 420 cm^{-1} : CNC deformation.

Glimepiride shows sharp peaks at 3369 cm^{-1} and 3288 cm^{-1} due to N-H stretching, 1707 cm^{-1} and 1674 cm^{-1} due to carbonyl group, 1345 cm^{-1}

showing C-N stretching vibration, and 1153 cm^{-1} showing S=O. stretching vibration. FTIR stretching of C=O. group is at 1656-1715 cm^{-1} and stretching of C-H bond at 2922 cm^{-1} . The peaks slightly shift in different batches at 2954, 2873, 2837, 2886, 2939, and 2933 cm^{-1} respectively. FTIR spectra of PVA show absorption peaks from the PVA, including: O-H stretching: At about 3300 cm^{-1} , C-O stretching: At around 1085 cm^{-1} , Asymmetric CH₂ stretching: At around 2910 cm^{-1} . The spectra of crystalline and amorphous lactose contain bands at 3600-3200 cm^{-1} , 1650 cm^{-1} and 1200-1070 cm^{-1} . The main IR spectral shifts from 3371 to 3,347 cm^{-1} and 1693 to 1682 cm^{-1} , as well as from 3094 to 3136 cm^{-1} and 1718 to 1735 cm^{-1} for Saccharin suggested that the O single bond H and N single bond H groups in both chemical structures were taken part in a hydrogen bonding.

Figure No, 10. FTIR Interpretation Data**Table No, 17. FTIR Interpretation of Pure Drug and Compounds**

Sl.No	Compounds	Functional Group				
		C=C	C=O	N-H	C-H	O-H
	Standard Frequency	1450-1600	1820-1660	3400	3000-2850	3600-2400
1	Metformin	3294	1634	3294	-	3369
2	Glimepiride	1345	1707	3369	2922	3288
3	Sodium saccharin	-	1693	-	-	3,347
4	Lactose	-	1650	-	-	3200
5	PVA	1085	-	-	2910	3369
6	Metformin+ Glimepiride	3294	1634	3294	2922	3369

Stability studies

Stability studies were done for the optimized formulation (F4) at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ /, 75 of RH $\pm$ 5 RH

as per the standard guidelines and the results are summarized in the table 18

Table No, 18. Stability Studies

Parameters		Time Minutes	10 Days	20 Days	30 Days
<i>In-vitro</i> drug release profile	API I	40	94.65	94.61	92.9
	API II	10	8.83	9.03	9.10
		20	40.81	40.98	42.12
		30	71.59	71.59	71.64
		40	99.10	98.64	98.15

Stability studies were done for the optimized formulation (F3) at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, 75 of RH $\pm$ 5 RH as per the standard guidelines and there is no significant change in the drug content and the drug release from the optimized formulation (F3).

CONCLUSION

The Medicated chewing gum containing anti-diabetic drug is formulated successively by using hydrophilic swellable polymer. The formulations were validated in terms of thickness, hardness, weight variation and friability, drug content, swelling index, in-vitro drug release study, stability study and FT-IR studies. All the formulations were shown fairly acceptable data for all the parameters evaluated for the drug polymer ratio 1.4: 0.6 (F1) shows the drug release (API I - 99, API II - 64) at the end of 40 minutes the concentration of wheat prolamin and high concentration of PVA. Which shows the minimal drug release rate of API II from the MCG. The

drug-polymer ratio 1.6: 0.4 (F2) shows the drug release (API I - 97.9, API II - 71.17) at the end of 40 minutes the high concentration of wheat prolamin and high concentration of PVA. Which shows the less drug release API I and minimal drug release rate of API II from the MCG. This less amount of drug release from the formulation due to the combination of two polymer ratios. The drug-polymer ratio 1.8:0.2 (F3) shows the drug release (API I - 98.5, API II - 98.65) at the end of 40 minutes the optimized concentration of wheat prolamin and PVA. Which shows the optimized combination of the formulation was release the drug in a controlled manner. The drug-polymer ratio 2.0:0.05 (F4) shows the drug release (API I - 72.54, API II - 78.75) at the end of 40 minutes the higher concentration of wheat prolamins and very low concentration of PVA. This ratio of polymers reduced the concentration of drug release from the formulation.

Formulation	Zero Order Kinetics		First Order Kinetics		Higuchi's Kinetics		Korsmeyer Peppas Kinetics	
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²
F3	10.924	0.994	-0.091	0.993	10.732	0.910	31.714	0.995

The formulation F1, F2 formulated by using the less quantity of polymer ratio, shows high drug release profile within the duration. The formulation F4 shows less drug release profile in the duration of time, hence reaching the maximum release of drug with maximizing the time, with this the chance of patient complains will decreases. In the optimized polymer ratio in F3 will shows better drug release profile in the duration of time. From the data observed with in vitro drug release the optimized formulation of F3 polymer ratio releases the drug from the formulation in a controlled manner and the maximum amount of drug released from the matrix in the course of duration. From the various kinetic model for Medicated chewing

gum, it can be concluded that the F3 showing Korsmeyer Peppas kinetic as the plot of the model shown higher regression ($R^2=0.995$). The release mechanism can be concluded that diffusion controlled mechanism. From the results of stability data provided, it can be concluded that the formulation was stable at the condition 40°C /75 RH for one month. All the parameters like drug content of the MCG and consistency in dissolution studies even after simulating extreme consistency during their storage. From this above discussion it is concluded the MCG containing anti diabetic drug, good means of promising therapy which achieving higher patient compliance.

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HOW TO CITE : Hemamalini Saravanan, K. L. Senthil Kumar, Formulation And Evaluation Of Medicated Chewing Gum Containing Metformin And Glimepiride, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 4, 503-520. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10943964>